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Digitally Mediated Nature: Assessing the Role of Digital Tools in Employing Nature-Based Solutions to Urban Sustainability

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ABSTRACT

As digital technologies are increasingly using nature to address urban sustainability governance, we need to better understand how this affects human-nature relationships. Investigating seven pilot cities in an EU-funded Research and Innovation project, we critically examine the aims and implementation of digitally mediated nature in urban contexts. Drawing on interviews with stakeholders responsible for implementing solutions locally, we reveal the tensions involved in enrolling nature in pre-defined and expert-driven technological solutions. Our findings problematize the way the promotion of urban nature is funded by the EU and others, where requirements of technological readiness and quantification undermine more relational approaches to human-nature interconnections.

KEYWORDS

nature-based solutions; cities; EU; co-design; nature; relationality

Introduction

Cities are increasingly looking to nature to meet several societal challenges (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016). Green spaces that urban-nature projects provide are recognized for the various ecosystem services they bring to urban areas (Elmqvist et al., 2015). Nature-based solutions are a dominant approach to strengthening the presence of nature in urban contexts, and it is an approach favored by policymakers and funders such as the European Union (Remme and Haarstad, 2022). There has been a surge of research and policy initiatives on nature-based solutions and ecosystem services in Europe, supported by the European Commission through the EU's Biodiversity Strategy (Maes and Jacobs, 2017), but also a range of other agenda-setting institutions such as the World Bank and the United Nations. In other words, there is a strong policy-drive to implement natural solutions in urban contexts in Europe and elsewhere. The emergence of nature has coincided with an increasing attention and optimism towards digitalization of urban environments. In an increasingly digitized society, nature-based solutions are now becoming “smarter” (Li and Nassauer,

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2021) and oriented towards circularity (Katsou et al, 2020), as cities are looking for innovative technologies to achieve sustainability targets (Kitchin et al., 2019).

Technology can provide new experiences with nature and acceptance of nature-based solutions (Jepson and Ladle, 2015; Li and Nassauer, 2021). At the same time, there is also a wide-ranging critical discussion of the risk of instrumentalizing nature, in the context of a rise of technocracy within environmental and sustainability governance (Randrup et al., 2020; Kotsila et al., 2021; Moss et al., 2021; Tozer et al., 2023). Through solutions ranging from no-tech to high-tech (Snep et al., 2020), nature is being brought online and “programmed as infrastructure” (Gabrys, 2022) and “gamified” (Istrate and Hamel, 2023). Critics suggest that digitally mediated nature limits the experience and representation of nature, and when used for management purposes, there is a risk that only particular types of values are integrated into environmental governance (Kenter, 2018). When major funders like the EU advance nature-based solutions and aim to use digital tools to gain knowledge of what happens in urban environments, they promote particular types and conceptions of nature and downplay others (Remme and Haarstad, 2022).

As digital technologies are increasingly used to enroll nature in urban sustainability governance, we need to better understand how this affects human-nature relationships. This article examines the way nature is mediated in the governance and implementation of urban sustainability projects relying on digitization. It contributes empirically based insights on the enrollment of nature in technology-driven projects, and a critical discussion of the tensions involved in enrolling nature in pre-defined and expert-driven technological solutions. This helps problematize the funding models of these projects, as requirements of technological readiness and quantification undermine more relational approaches to human–nature interconnections.

The empirical basis for the article is our research on experiences with digitally mediated nature-based solutions in seven pilot cities in an EU-funded Research and Innovation project, a project in which the authors are partners. By implementing nature-based solutions in pilot cities, the project aimed to integrate technological solutions into green spaces to enhance the health and well-being of citizens. With the use of city dashboards, a gaming application, and a range of other digital tools, the objective was to allow citizens to gain knowledge about the state of the immediate environment that they could use to engage with nature and make informed decisions about their own behavior.

The project has arguably been highly innovative, and it, therefore, provides a good opportunity to observe tensions between technology and nature in urban space. We have studied the early phases of the implementation process in the seven pilot cities, which aimed to use co-creation processes to facilitate citizen involvement in the implementation of technologically enhanced nature-based solutions. In the analysis we applied a relational lens to investigate the motivation and framing of digitally mediated urban sustainability projects. We did so by building upon a typology of re-connect, re-think, and re-structure conceptualized through relational values of nature (Mattijssen et al., 2020).

In the article we argue that digital solutions are, in the governance models applied, typically layered on top of nature-based solutions rather than having a core function for urban nature itself. By monitoring, quantifying and gamifying nature, digital

solutions risk instrumentalizing nature within the governance models that are applied. Substantive co-design of technical solutions with citizens in technologically driven nature-based solutions is difficult, since digital innovation processes are not properly structured to allow for citizen input in large-scale innovation projects of this type. This problematizes the existing funding models of these types of urban sustainability projects, whereby technological readiness and quantification predetermine which technological tools are used and that undermines both citizen involvement in developing solutions as well as more relational approaches to human-nature interconnections.

The article proceeds with a literature review regarding the digitalization of cities, the role of nature in cities, and conceptualizations of nature. We then move on to the analytical framework presenting the typology of re-connect, re-think, and re-structure. Moving on to the methodology, we introduce the methods applied before presenting the result of our analysis. A discussion follows where we further explore the results in more detail and present our concluding thoughts.

Nature and Technology in the Urban Context

Bringing Nature into the Digitalized City

In conceptual terms, this article addresses the intersection between technology, nature, and the city. This intersection has already been examined and debated across several strands of literature, each with its own priorities and assumptions. The linkages between cities and technological systems are often framed in terms of “the smart city,” or alternatively, “the digital city” or the “intelligent city”—such hyped terms have become highly prevalent in business, government, research, and media, as ample literature on the subject illustrates (Das, 2020; Joss et al., 2017; de Jong et al., 2015; Haarstad and Wathne, 2019; Albino et al., 2015).

The work on technological enhancement and digital mediation of urban contexts has largely overlooked the natural environment. Moss et al. (2021) argued that little attention has been paid to the role of nature in digitally mediated urban environments. But this seems to be changing rapidly. Nature is on the agenda in cities and new concepts are emerging with cities being framed as “sponge cities,” “forest cities,” “livable cities,” “green cities,” “eco cities,” among others (Cheng et al., 2022; de Jong et al., 2015). There are emerging strands of theorizing that attempt to center the role of nature in the city, for example through a post-anthropocentric approach that acknowledges a more-than-human urban future (Sheikh et al., 2023; Yigitcanlar et al., 2019). This is happening at a time when cities are increasing green spaces with pocket-parks, urban gardens, green roofs and walls, street trees, and other green infrastructures.

These strategies are typically recognized as nature-based solutions. As an umbrella concept, “nature-based solutions” covers a range of disciplines from green infrastructure, environmental engineering, ecosystem-based adaptation, to ecosystem service monitoring (Pauleit et al., 2017). Through different institutions, research, and policies, nature-based solutions have gained traction in both policymaking and research circles as a way to promote urban sustainability (Kotsila et al., 2021). The IUCN (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016), defines nature-based solutions as “actions to protect, sustainably manage,

and restore natural or modified ecosystems to address societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits.”

More recently, digital technologies have been introduced as an innovative approach to enhance and manage urban nature (Li et al., 2022). Nature is then being brought “online” through the “Internet of nature” (Galle et al., 2019). “Smart” solutions combined with green infrastructure can identify where there is a need for nature-based solutions and thus promote the greening of cities (Anguluri and Narayanan, 2017). Trees as bioindicators can provide in situ monitoring, making cities not only smart but also green at the same time (Luvisi and Lorenzini, 2014). “Smart” blue-green roofs can retain and reuse water (Snep et al., 2020), and GIS maps and tools can contribute to an increased knowledge base for decisions regarding urban green spaces (Crnčević et al., 2017). Citizen participation is also recognized as a vital part of nature-based solutions (Wickenberg et al., 2021; Raymond et al., 2017; Wamsler et al. 2020). Therefore, there seems to be a great deal of optimism in policy circles and governance institutions about the benefits of urban nature.

At the same time, there is reason to be cautious. The efficiency of these solutions may be hindered by the rise of technocracy within environmental and sustainability governance (Randrup et al., 2020; Kotsila et al., 2021; Remme and Haarstad, 2022). Additionally, there is a need to examine critically the wider cultural and social significance of the various technologies employed and the way nature is put to the service of other goals, such as climate resilience (Tozer et al., 2023). When nature is deployed to achieve societal aims (however laudable these aims may be), there is a risk that nature is reduced and instrumentalized through processes, measurements, and monitoring in governance (Silva et al., 2018; Kaika, 2017).

In the governance processes to achieve these aims, challenges still exist regarding how to balance citizens’ needs with expert knowledge, planners’ roles, the disconnect between short-term and long-term actions, and budget constraints (Kabisch et al., 2016). Moving beyond technical engineering aims means coming to terms with dominant views of technology as neutral or objective (Kitchin et al., 2015) and thinking about how ecological benefits can be experienced in a socially inclusive manner (Kotsila et al., 2021). The empowerment of citizens through nature-based solutions thus requires the willingness of urban governance to encourage flexibility and holistic approaches (Kvamsås, 2021). Scholars have argued that this will require a departure from technocratic path dependence highlighting technological rationality (Deely et al., 2020; Kuitert and van Buuren, 2022).

However, we need better understanding of the tensions between nature on the one hand, and instrumental governance aims on the other, in processes of implementing digital solutions in urban spaces. This article seeks to build on and complement the literature on the integration of nature in smart and digital solutions discussed above. In order to do this, in the following sections we will in the following sections explore literature that conceptualizes the value of nature in cities.

Urban Political Ecology: Conceptualizing the Relationality of Nature in Cities

Separately from the literature on ecosystem services and nature-based solutions discussed above, there is ample scholarly work that reflects on the assumed role nature

plays in urban development and how nature is framed in urban interventions. Drawing on urban political ecology, it problematizes the typical assumption in Western epistemology that a city is something opposite to nature (Heynen et al., 2006), and society has been emancipated from nature through scientific and technological progress (Kaika, 2017). Even though these are long-standing and well-known critiques, mainstream governance models are still to a significant extent, based on these assumptions, managing nature from a top-down, expert driven perspective based on quantitative criteria (Karvonen and Yocom, 2011). Certainly, mainstream governance of nature-based solutions is still at risk of harboring such assumptions about nature (Remme and Haarstad, 2022; Tozer et al., 2023).

In contrast, urban political ecology has advanced theoretical understandings of the interconnectedness and co-constructedness of nature and the city (Tzaninis et al., 2021). The city has come to be understood less as a distinct physical object and more as a set of relationships situated in a wider web of relations and metabolisms, including both natural and technological relations. These perspectives are useful in helping to unpack how, who, and why nature is being enrolled in particular ways, and what the effects are.

We are particularly interested in how the insights help us unpack the enrollment of nature in technologically oriented urban sustainability projects, in our case using nature-based solutions as a policy approach. As solutions are framed as “natural” or “unnatural,” nature-based solutions may uphold a binary view of nature as something external, outside of sociopolitical associations (Osaka et al., 2021). The relational perspective from urban political ecology offers a way of exploring how cities are co-evolving through nature and with technologies. Such a perspective opens for a critical view of instrumental forms of nature, whereby nature is framed through monitoring and indicator frameworks and ecosystem services (Kull et al., 2015).

Several authors have pointed to the potential for a more holistic approach towards urban nature, where society must rethink its relationship to the natural world, recognize the long-term cyclical ecological processes and that these cycles do not follow the cycles of political change (Nelson et al., 2020). Randrup et al. (2020), for example, have suggested that we move away from the linear one-way relationship between humans and nature, towards a positive feedback loop based on a community-ecological perspective. Understanding human behavior with socio-ecological interactions through relational values becomes increasingly important (Pineda-Pinto et al., 2021; Chan et al., 2018). There are some signs that such a perspective is making its way into mainstream science and governance perspectives. Some cities, like Berlin, have spawned a rich variety of digital nature schemes. Nevertheless, Moss et al. (2021) argue that these schemes still rely on anthropocentric notions of nature, with detrimental effects for nature.

Therefore, we need to better understand the process of integration of nature and technology in urban governance practices. It is unclear whether urban sustainability projects, as currently conceived and implemented, amplify the disconnect between citizens and nature (Colding and Barthel, 2017) or whether they are able to acknowledge citizens relations to nature, as values are not absolute or given (Ernstson and Sörlin, 2013). These are crucial considerations, and relational values can potentially contribute to a more nuanced and ethical transformation towards sustainability (Himes and Muraca, 2018; West et al., 2018).

This article responds to the need for a better understanding of the enrollment of nature in urban governance practices by examining a concrete effort aiming to implement solutions in specific pilot projects—in this case a Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation project with seven pilot cities. This can help unpack the processes through which nature is enrolled and mediated in urban sustainability projects and provide insights into the tensions that are generated. To do so, the article employs an analytical framework that allows us to explore variations of relational values of nature through empirical analysis.

Analytical Framework and Methodology

In order to examine critically the integration of technological and nature-based solutions in concrete contexts, we employ the typology by Mattijssen et al. (2020) based on Abson et al. (2017), exploring relational values of nature through the categories of re-connect, re-think, and re-structure. The framework emphasizes people's connection to nature (re-connect), knowledge production (re-think), and the role of institutions (re-structure). As unsustainable practices are still enduring, Abson and et al. (2017) introduced the typology with the aim of advancing sustainability through underlying leverage points.

Building on this framework, Mattijssen et al. (2020) argue for the integration of relational values of nature framework as a leverage point for nature policy in Europe. One of the ways to achieve this is to re-connect citizens with nature through digitalization of nature practices. With this as the starting point of our analysis, we critically examine the purpose of digital solutions in engaging citizens with nature. As we understand technology to be a social construct, i.e., value-laden (Feenberg, 2010), we use that typology to investigate: the aim of the digital solutions (re-connect), what values of nature are mediated through the digital solutions (re-think), and how citizens are involved in the decision-making process (re-structure).

The empirical basis for this article is based on our research on opportunities and challenges for governance in the implementation of nature-based solutions in seven pilot cities of a Horizon 2020-funded Research and Innovation project, a project in which we were partners. The aim of the pilot projects was to create safe and inclusive public green spaces that enhance biodiversity and health and well-being for citizens through innovative nature-based solutions. The specific interventions which are using information and communication technology (ICT) to collect data through sensors and devices in the project are listed in Table 1. The data collected through these sensors are monitored through Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to measure the effectiveness of the innovative solutions following the needs of the localities. The data will be visualized on a health and well-being platform, where citizens can gain knowledge about their environment through sensor data. Citizens will also be engaged through wearables and a gaming application that offers virtual and augmented reality.

The objective is not only to bring nature into the city, but to advance citizens' perceptions of nature in public spaces. A diverse set of stakeholders are involved in the participatory process through co-creation including co-identification, co-design, co-implementation, and co-monitoring. The data obtained from the KPIs will be evaluated across the different pilots to find best practices that will feed into locally adapted sustainable models.

Table 1: The different projects in the pilot cities and some of the digital components

Pilot City	Project Objectives	Digital Components
Italian City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enhance nature-based solutions in historical garden - Improve citizens' health and well-being through blue and green areas - Develop a "local observatory on therapeutic effects of the landscape" - Improved accessibility of garden routes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring of microclimate - ICT and virtual tools to ensure visitors' safety and a positive experience - Touch screen installed outside the garden with visualized environmental monitored data, videos, images, and sounds of the garden
Irish City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Outdoor learning hub at library and museum quarter - Removal of car parking spaces - Host shared functions - Sensory garden for health and well-being - Rainwater harvest system encouraging citizens towards sustainable user of water 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Showcasing newest technologies - Virtual learning pod sensors collecting number of visitors and duration of stay - LED lights for improved public lighting - Sensor equipped bike-stations to better understand the use of the space
Greek City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mobile urban living room (MULaR) with a convertible construction - Citizens' relationship with public space and nature - Social and cultural activities - Assess the state of green spaces and propose improvements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collect data on urban environment and citizens' health and well-being - Interactive mobile apps and games - Mixed reality applications - Sensors on bikes and bike-stations to measure pollutants and health measurements
Maltese City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Micro greening in street with participatory design process - Urban biodiversity with nature-based solutions - Intervention at a school and Gzira Gardens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Citizen science to measure air and noise quality to increase awareness of health and well-being
Belgian City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regeneration of former hospital site - Temporary mobile urban living room for cultural activities until construction of new performing arts building is completed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - IoT with smart lighting pole monitoring noise through sensors - Sensors measuring water quality in river - Mobility sensors measuring the number of cyclists and pedestrians that connect to other projects of the municipality - Measurement of local climatic conditions
Slovenian City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sports and recreational park - Greening of military brownfield with indigenous plants - Sustainable forest trails connecting facilities - Interconnection of sports, recreational, and therapeutic facilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ICT platform to manage the sports and recreational facilities - IoT sensors in the park - Monitoring number of visitors and movement - IoT through wearables to track activity and monitor health and well-being of visitors
Swedish City	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transformation of old landfill area - Improve waterways and creation of a wetland bed to increase biodiversity - Improve environmental awareness through education on climate change and biodiversity - Open-air classroom with bee hotels and insect habitats 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart lighting contributing to an inviting environment and encouraging activities in the area

The informants are the pilot leaders and pilot experts across the seven pilot cities. The interview material involves in-depth interviews with key personnel in all pilot cities of the project, with at least two from each pilot city. "Pilot leaders" are the leaders of implementation in each pilot city, and these are in most cases local government officials. "Pilot experts" have been designated as responsible for assisting the pilot cities, and these are consultants, architects, project managers, and in some cases researchers at universities. The aim was to interview both pilot leaders and pilot experts from the cities, although

Table 2: Overview of informants and their role in the project

No.	Background	Role in the Project
1	Project manager	Pilot leader
2	Senior project manager	Pilot expert
3	Architect	Pilot expert
4	Researcher	Pilot expert
5	Landscape architect	Pilot leader
6	Consultant	Pilot leader
7	University lecturer	Pilot leader/expert
8	Architect	Pilot expert
9	Senior executive engineer	Pilot leader
10	Project manager	Pilot leader
11	Consultant	Pilot expert
12	Researcher	Pilot expert
13	University lecturer	Pilot leader/expert
14	Researcher	Pilot expert
15	Researcher	Pilot expert
16	Pilot leader	Pilot leader
17	Researcher	Pilot expert
18	Researcher	Pilot expert

in some cases these roles overlapped. There are in total 18 informants (See [Table 2](#) for an overview of informants).

Through semi-structured interviews with project partners tasked with implementation, we asked how digital solutions are framed, how they are intended to enhance the nature-based solutions, how citizens are drawn into the co-design process, and how they serve to connect citizens to nature. The interviews were thus semi-structured, keeping an open dialogue around the topic as their answers provided guidance for further inquiry. As the pilot cities are implementing various solutions, the interview guides focused on the specific pilot cities objectives, while asking more general questions concerning their view on the integration of technology alongside nature-based solutions. The interviews were conducted online between October 2022 and March 2023, each lasting between 20 and 60 minutes. The interviews were conducted through Teams, and we were granted permission to record audio for transcription.

Additionally, a document analysis of relevant deliverables and research articles from the project was conducted to add more context and depth to the data material. The deliverables pertained to the knowledge baseline of the pilot cities regarding e.g., the co-creation strategy and experience with participatory governance.

Results and Analysis

Across the seven pilot cities, the project worked with local municipalities and other partners to upgrade and create new green spaces—and in these spaces provide citizens with innovative solutions that make it easier for them to engage with nature and improve their own health and well-being. The project had ambitious plans for including citizens in the development of these solutions. With a strong digital component, one aim of the project was to implement “an entire ecosystem of fully connected intelligent sensors and devices.” This was done by developing a sensor network alongside a digital health and wellbeing platform to “allow for a true digitization of green spaces.” While the cases provided somewhat different experiences of public spaces, the common objective was the

implementation of innovative digital solutions based on “visionary ideas” that will add value to citizens’ engaging with urban nature.

In the following, we will discuss the findings of the project using our analytical categories that emphasize people’s connections to nature (re-connect), knowledge production (re-think), and the role of institutions (re-structure).

Re-Connect: Bringing Citizens Closer to Nature in Urban Areas

In this first analytical section, we present our results concerning how the pilot cities worked to re-connect citizens with urban nature through technological means. Described as the “heart” of the project, the cross-pilot health and well-being platform aimed to blend the physical and digital together. One informant (16) explained this as a “green visualization.” In this way, the pilot cities aspired to use technology to make nature accessible for all citizens in the green spaces in the pilot projects.

Throughout the interviews, it was clear how the project had ambitions to use digital technologies to improve citizens’ experiences of different urban environments. One informant (9) commented that one goal for the project was “to take what’s effectively a poorly used, unattractive space and turn it into a space for use by all.” In the Italian pilot smart benches were installed alongside mobile apps to allow citizens to navigate the area better. Similar efforts were made in the Slovenian pilot, where one digital solution focused on enabling access for disabled people in and around the facilities. As one informant (1) said about visually impaired people, “we did a part of the park that is intended for them to learn how to move in the natural environment.”

The digital components are described to enhance environmental awareness and influence the daily lives of citizens. Sensors provide citizens with real-time information about the urban environment that can influence citizens’ behavior and knowledge. Another example concerned the Greek city that visualizes air pollution particles through augmented reality on a screen, and promotes behavior that reduces air pollution. The Belgian city plans to install smart lighting poles with a noise ringing, “telling [citizens] to be quiet” if the noise exceeds a certain limit (informant 3). Sensor data on temperature can be used as “nudging” information, e.g., showing how much lower the temperature is under a tree in the summer.

The pilot leaders and experts we interviewed were concerned with not having data just for its own sake, but in order to “add something to a conversation” (informant 2), by improving knowledge about nature and enhancing the experience of visiting green spaces. For example, the sensors provide information on how many visitors are in a particular green space, which one informant (2) said can make it easier to plan and to make sure potential visitors have a good experience. Sensor data can further be used to invite people into green spaces, as in the case of the Italian city where the space is behind walls, and a digital “totem” will provide information with the aim of inviting citizens into the garden.

There is significant optimism in the overarching project about the way technology can enhance the experience of nature—but this was not necessarily shared by those in charge of local implementation. Regarding the gaming application (See [Figure 1](#)) developed in the project, one informant (2) described how they do not think people want to use an app in nature and that the purpose of visiting a park is that “you are trying to disconnect from

Figure 1: screen capture from the *Go Nature* app, gamifying nature in urban space. *Source: project website.*

mobiles.” There have been some discussions in workshops regarding virtual reality and augmented reality, whereby “people struggle with that because the idea is that you’re trying to connect with nature and you shouldn’t be looking at, sort of something in the virtual world or augmented world.”

These comments were in line with the overall view of technology in green spaces, which was met with some apprehension by the local actors interviewed—illustrating tensions between the overarching EU-funded project and the implementation on the ground. Citizen stakeholders as well as some of the project partners sometimes contested the notion that nature and technology could be integrated. From the interviews and document analysis, it was evident how being in nature is, in an ideal sense, associated with the absence of technology. Statements were made about how one must get away from technology to connect with nature and one participant in a workshop was surprised that there is “so much” technology that will be present.

Across the pilots and in the overarching project, there are high ambitions of integrating technology and nature in urban spaces. The project involves high-tech solutions, and a common platform across the pilots for sharing data and visualizing them—this has been promised in the General Agreement signed with the EU. At the same time, our interviews illustrate how the project aimed at engaging citizens with nature through digital solutions is not without apprehension. The integration of digital solutions and nature does not necessarily correspond with conceptions of what nature is—which we elaborate in the next section on framings of nature.

Re-Think: Challenging Conventional Framings of Nature?

Another aim of the project is shaping future cities towards health and well-being of citizens, whereby the public spaces in cities become fully “people-centered.” With over 30 KPIs, the effectiveness of the planned solutions is monitored and evaluated concerning challenges found in the pilot cities, such as climate mitigation and adaptation, water management, green space management, air quality, urban regeneration, and more. The KPIs are to some extent adjusted toward each pilot’s specific needs, by mapping which KPIs are relevant to the pilots’ visionary solutions. Following this, the KPIs were linked to several challenges: climate change mitigation and adaptation, water management, green space management, air quality, urban regeneration, participatory planning and governance, social cohesion and justice, public health, and potential for new economic opportunities and green jobs.

The aim is to explore the commonalities between the interventions in different cities with various climatic conditions across Europe, to cross evaluate the results and find best practices. As explained by an informant (12), this can be if there had been improvement in air quality in one pilot city and not in another, then, solutions used in one place could be used to decrease air pollution in another. The data from sensors will be visualized with KPIs on several dashboards on the digital health and wellbeing platform for different user experiences, with overview of all pilots, pilot-specific indicators, a 3-D view of the pilot site, biodiversity data, and a survey asking how the site makes citizens feel (See Figure 2).

In a sense, the project advanced a range of different values, from instrumental to intrinsic and relational. Instrumental values include the regulation and provision of ecosystem services, such as decreases in daytime temperature and access to green space. Intrinsic values are found with attention to biodiversity and species richness, such as an increase of pollinators. In terms of relational values of nature, they can be found in the aim of using the digital solutions to increase awareness of urban

Figure 2: the dashboards to be included on the H&WB platform. *Source: website of project*

ecosystems. These include social learning concerning urban ecosystems and their functions/services (one of the pilots), social values for urban ecosystems and biodiversity (three pilots), and perceptions of citizens about urban nature (four pilots). Other relational values include social cohesion, i.e., participation (all pilots), feeling of improving quality of life (six pilots), perceived well-being before and after a visit to green space (two pilots), sense of place (one pilot) and residential attachment and satisfaction (two pilots).

However, interventions focusing on responsibility and care towards nature are not explicitly included in the project. While improved environmental awareness can motivate pro-environmental behavior, it is not directly connected to reciprocal human-nature interactions. However, relational values are included to an extent in the questionnaire for perceptions of the effects of citizens on urban nature. Here, citizens are asked about sustainability efforts they are following, and to agree or disagree with statements about greening interventions, i.e., “it will not be well maintained by the community and local administration,” and “it makes people more caring and respectful towards the environment.”

Regarding the use of questionnaires to measure relational KPIs, one informant (12) explained the challenge with this as “it’s not always easy to quantify qualitative data because it’s very subjective.” This was shared by another informant (13) who commented on how choosing the questions was the hardest part, while also making sure that the survey was not too long. The local actors struggled to include relational questions in the survey for the cross-pilot digital health and wellbeing platform, as it was seen as subjective and thereby not easy to quantify. At the time of the analysis the version available includes a feedback dashboard where citizens can answer: “how does the site make you feel?” “how do you think the pilot site looks?” and “how comfortable are you?” (See [Figure 3](#)).

There was also an opportunity to include more relational values on the platform, as the KPIs displayed were prioritized based on a scoring system. Environmental wellness was included in the environmental and ecological category that only one of the pilots chose as a high priority criteria to be included on the ICT platform, which emphasizes “a sustainable lifestyle, protecting natural resources, eliminating pollutants and excessive waste, and providing adequate management of natural resources.”

With the KPI framework, there is a clear risk that nature is reduced to quantitative forms of representation. One informant (12) explained that government officials will not treat long texts but have to see numbers in order to accept that something is a success. Qualitative forms of measurement were also seen as more time consuming, which was problematic given the timelines of the project. As one informant (12) said, “we have to consider the fact that other pilot cities might not have the expertise to conduct qualitative research ... keeping it a bit simpler in a way is better so that we’ll have fewer difficulties comparing the data and evaluating data.”

Across the pilots, we see how the cities have tried to include types of values in the evaluation system written into the General Agreement with the EU—the KPIs. To some extent the KPIs involve relational values of nature—but the interview data also suggests that this inclusion is fraught with tension. The informants saw problems in translating qualitative values into quantitative indicators, and it is also clear how the KPIs leave out certain qualitative aspects, such as care for nature.

How does the site make you feel?

Figure 3: example from feedback dashboard on the H&WB platform. *Source: website of project*

Re-Structure: Challenging Existing Governance Models?

The project is also implementing a co-creation strategy throughout all phases of the project, with co-identification, co-design, co-implementation, and co-evaluation of the visionary solutions. The early phases of the co-creation included workshops with focus groups, where the pilots utilized the stakeholder mapping that was done initially. From the interviews it was clear how this challenged traditional participatory methods, as the pilots were more intentional in who they invited to participate and exploring new ways of engagement. In the first workshop, stakeholders could contribute to co-identifying needs and barriers to the solutions. The input was used to further validate and refine the solutions that was re-introduced in the second workshop.

When asked about institutional challenges, the informants shared how they have collaborated well in the pilots between different levels of expertise. There were no signs of “silo” thinking and as one informant (2) said, “the sites actually had a good idea of what their solutions were already.” At the same time, one informant discussed how their role as “expert” was challenged as they tried to understand what people wanted from the platform and to allow people to shape the user experience of digital tools. They discovered that, for citizens, the concrete elements of the green space projects were more important than the digital solutions. One informant (10) explained that “if you are talking about a park, it’s something [citizens] can relate to.” The pilot leaders learned to talk about what could be experienced at the pilot sites, instead of the technicalities. In this sense, the local expertise consisted less of technical skills and more in understanding local needs and negotiating this into the technical solutions advanced by the overarching project.

After the initial workshops, the digital solutions including the gaming *Go Nature* app and the digital health and wellbeing platform were disseminated in town hall meetings—as a way to involve citizens in co-creation. Town halls are described as public events that

Table 3: Examples of questions in Town Hall meeting regarding H&WB platform and the *Go Nature* app

Health and Well-Being Platform	<i>Go Nature</i> Application
Is the visualization of indicators on the platform understandable?	Did you like the demo video's graphics?
Do you want to suggest another kind of visualization?	Do you have any experience in augmented reality (AR)?
Would you like to see something additional on the platform?	Would you be interested in trying an AR experience through HoloLens? (Yes No) Do you find such an AR experience interesting? Do you think this could help you better understand the effects of air pollution, noise, temperature, etc? Have any other suggestions you'd like to share?

Table 4: Responses at Town Halls regarding the H&WB platform and the *Go Nature* app

Feedback from Town Halls
It could certainly help with greater understanding and perception of environmental data When it's only doing the measurements, it can be interesting for research; but not interesting for the citizens; there should be action taken to improve the situation Good to be able to access sensor data/information before visiting the park. The relevance was questioned and who made the game, didn't see relevance to [the project] with this game When there is a lot of noise pollution, what measures will be taken? Are actions linked to the results coming from measurements/sensors?

include everyone from citizens to civil servants. Here, one objective was to familiarize the stakeholders with the digital applications and gain feedback. A questionnaire was developed by project researchers, illustrated in Table 3. And as illustrated in Table 4, while some saw value in digital solutions, citizens also questioned the relevance of the platform for visitors to green spaces.

The input was used to further refine the design of the platform regarding placement, font, bench-mark data, and making data easily understandable. One reflection among the pilot experts after the first Town Halls was that the project should “give more thought to how this will be viewed and used on the site as people might want to get away from technology.” After the town halls, the project gathered more citizen input through smaller co-creation interventions, such as online surveys and a digital feedback box on the project webpage.

It was clear that working on the suggestions and requests from citizens on the digital platforms was a challenge. This challenge was explained by one informant (2) as a balance between what citizens want to do on the site, on the one hand, and staying true to the design of the digital solutions on the other. A part of this was the lack of digital expertise among citizens and local governance actors, relative to the competence required to actually help shape the digital tools. “We know very little about sensors,” said one informant (9) and went on to describe how the project has provided a learning curve for those who had been tasked with implementing them.

Furthermore, with a strong digital component, governance actors are dependent on outsourcing to obtain the technology needed. This narrows possibilities to what the companies they collaborate with can deliver, and how much money is available to pay for the services — problem one informant (5) described as “very narrowing.” This often leaves the pilot projects to rely on standardized and pre-existing solutions. One informant (2)

described how “many parts of the functionality were already set,” and what was left to give input on was pertaining to color and detailed design choices, or the location of the sensors.

As digital solutions were already decided on in the proposal phase of the project, it was less open deliberation with the stakeholders about which digital solutions were wanted or needed and why. The structure of the overarching project was also a challenge for local implementation. One informant (2) explained the problem of having input from stakeholders in seven different pilot sites for one platform. And as explained by another informant (9), starting off with no proposal for solutions would make it difficult to prioritize between different stakeholders’ interests. Yet the fact that solutions were largely predefined in the proposal stage presented significant problems for citizen engagement. As one informant (10) lamented, “We are coming with some possible solutions and then try to find out, who is interested in using them?”

Across the pilots, there were obvious tensions between the aims of active citizen inclusion on the one hand, and the more practical demands of the overarching project on the other. The informants shared concerns about how to balance what is in the Grant Agreement with the EU on the one hand, with its predefined solutions and KPIs, and local needs of the cities and the citizens on the other. As one said (informant 2), it was a “skill and an art” to balance these concerns.

Discussion

This article has set out to discuss the challenges involved with enrolling nature into urban sustainability governance using digitalization. The purpose was to contribute to an ongoing debate about the role and value of nature in digitally mediated urban environments, a debate that has growing relevance in the context of the strong policy focus on nature-based solutions, circularity, and digitalization of governance (Randrup et al., 2020; Kotsila et al., 2021; Moss et al., 2021; Tozer et al., 2023). Others have problematized the way nature is brought onboard in digital dashboards and games represent a technocratic form of governance that exercises control over nature through datafication (Kaika, 2017; Sheikh et al., 2023).

Examining one Horizon 2020-funded project with seven pilot cities, we explored how governance actors in concrete projects have grappled with these problems and how they reflect on the tensions involved. In several ways, our findings illustrate the ongoing challenges of managing the intersection of nature and technology in urban green spaces. First, we find that in re-connecting citizens with nature using various digital tools, such as city dashboards and gaming apps, inflated claims about the integration of technology and urban space are being made. Ironically perhaps, those who were tasked with the implementation of the project on the ground tended to see nature as the absence of technology. There was, paradoxically, a contrast between how the project overall framed the integration of nature and urban space and how those who implemented the project tended to see it. Informants saw technological solutions as add-ons, layered on top of real natural artifacts in urban space, and not key to the core functioning of nature-based solutions. For instance, the aim of digital solutions in enhancing environmental awareness and engaging children was viewed as beneficial, but not critical to how green spaces work in cities. There is still a long way from being exposed to the visualization of CO₂

emissions or air quality, to acting in ways to enhance environmental sustainability or appreciating the intrinsic values of nature. There is a risk that quantifying and reducing natural processes in this way instrumentalizes nature rather than creating stronger relationships between humans and nature.

Second, our empirical analysis reveals the tensions of involving citizens in the decision-making process of co-designing digital tools for nature-based solutions. While the project had high ambitions for citizen involvement, there are significant challenges in involving citizens when digital solutions are pre-defined, expert-driven, and often developed outside of the institutional boundaries of local governments. The project has encouraged a user-centric approach towards the co-design of the platform, where different skills and expectations are considered (Young et al., 2021). In line with previous studies, we find that citizens' involvement is reduced to re-arranging details of the platform within the boundaries of pre-existing objectives (Cardullo and Kitchin, 2019). This is a noted challenge within EU-funded Research and Innovation projects (O'Sullivan et al., 2020; Kitchin, 2019). Complementing these previous studies, we illustrate how attempts at digitally mediating nature in cities involved additional tensions, in the sense that natural processes and technological innovation processes are challenging to reconcile in citizen co-design processes.

Conclusion

By illustrating the tensions involved in implementing digitally mediated nature-based solutions on the ground in the pilot cities, the article shows that the urban governance models applied struggle to involve relational values of nature. Relying on quantification and gamification, and expert-driven technological design, these models struggle to involve the intrinsic values of nature—instead digital solutions become add-ons and layered on top of urban nature. From a relational point of view, digitally mediated nature-based solutions do not really bring citizens any closer to nature—to the contrary it places nature within the evaluative schematics central to visions of smart urban governance. While digital technologies are intended to enhance experiences with urban nature, they tend to simply provide a layer on top of natural artifacts that enable nature to be quantified, gamified, or measured.

A key problem, we would argue, comes from the way many of these projects are funded. The promotion of urban nature-based solutions is, to a large extent funded by the EU and other major funding organizations, — including the project examined in this article. Programs like Horizon 2020 and now Horizon Europe frame these governance activities as innovations and funds projects that advance the innovative competitiveness of Europe. This “projectification” of urban governance imposes a particular governance logic on these projects (Munck af Rosenschöld and Wolf, 2017).

We see several reasons for this. First, technological solutions have to be predefined at the application stage, in order to show technological readiness and to create a competitive proposal. Second, this logic enhances the expert-driven character of governance, since scientific competence and excellence are key evaluation criteria. And third, it quantifies the relationship to nature through the use of key performance indicators that project managers have to use to show that projects are progressing according to plan and are having a societal impact. In many ways, our locally based informants were struggling

against this logic of projectification when they were working to implement nature-based solutions in the pilot cities.

In place of technologically driven projects, there is a need to find other ways of knowing and relating to nature in urban policy and planning practice. Funding models should be opened up more to allow co-creation within existing realities on the ground. Alternative representations of nature may then be acknowledged that go beyond technical know-how and expert opinion, and to acknowledge the co-dependence of human and non-human lifeforms (Maller, 2021). Practitioners would be advised to use technology critically in such projects, and limit digital solutions to interventions where they serve a clear purpose for urban nature.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors report no conflicting interests. Readers should be aware that the authors were partners in the project discussed in the paper. They were only responsible for one task, which consisted of independent research on the governance challenges that the pilots faced during implementation of nature-based solutions.

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